

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B472
 Date: 29 July 2009
 Take Off: 07:35:30 Z Basel
 Landing: 11:41:30 Z Basel
 Flight Time: 4h 06m 00s

Campaign: CAVIAR
Operating Area: Jungfraujoch

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Luc Lathouwers	Directflight	
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight	
4	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM	
5	Mission Scientist 1	Chawn Harlow	Met Office	
6	AVAPS	Kate Turnbull	FAAM	
7	Cloud Physics	Phil Rosenberg	FAAM	
8	Core Chem / NOx	Stephane Bauguitte	FAAM	
9	SWS	Debbie O'Sullivan	Met Office	
10	ARIES/FWVS	Dave Tiddeman	Met Office	
11	MARSS	James Bowles	Met Office	
12	TAFTS	Paul Green	Imperial	Y
13	TAFTS 2	Ralph Beeby	Imperial	
14	Mission Scientist 2	Stuart Newman	Met Office	
15	CAA familiarisation	Richard Miller	CAA	
16				
17				
18				
19				

Missing Log Sheet	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
ViRC chat log	poor comms meant no useful ViRC during CAVIAR
Cloud Physics Processing	Processing yet to be completed.
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page
CVI	No log as no operator on CAVIAR

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	03 Nov 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

The following avi format video recordings should be available at the BADC in core_processed/faam-video :

faam-video-dfc_faam_20090729_r0_b472_081604_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090729_r0_b472_081802_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090729_r0_b472_091802_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090729_r0_b472_091948_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090729_r0_b472_102114_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20090729_r0_b472_081558_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090729_r0_b472_081807_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090729_r0_b472_101943_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090729_r0_b472_102107_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090729_r0_b472_112107_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20090729_r0_b472_081601_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20090729_r0_b472_081804_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20090729_r0_b472_091945_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20090729_r0_b472_102110_1hz.avi

No Digital8 video recordings were made on this flight.

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B472
 Date:29/7/09
 Project:CAVIAR
 Location:Jungfraujoch

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
070940		startup	0.70 kft	091	base l
071357		tow	0.70 kft	199	
071645		asp open	0.70 kft	330	
072631		taxy	0.70 kft	063	
073530		T/O	0.67 kft	154	
073630		cpc	2.6 kft	200	logging
080816	081632	Run 1	28.0 kft	146	
081503		Sonde 1	28.0 kft	145	
082130	082325	Run 2	28.0 kft	328	
082344	082558	Orbit 1	28.1 - 28.0 kft	346	
082627	082833	Orbit 2	28.1 kft	027	
082905	084222	Profile 1	28.0 - 15.0 kft	014	
084409	084626	Run 3	15.1 - 15.0 kft	138	
085034	085744	Run 4	15.0 kft	313	
085323		ovhd jfj	15.0 kft	320	
090439	090531	Run 4.1	15.0 kft	320	
091417	091617	Run 5	15.0 kft	149	
091506		ovhd jfj	15.0 kft	141	
091636	092000	Profile 2	15.0 - 19.0 kft	124	
092000	092947	Run 6	19.0 kft	323	
092210		ovhd jfj	19.0 kft	321	
093002	093456	Profile 3	19.0 - 24.0 kft	338	
093457	094235	Run 7	24.0 - 24.3 kft	143	
094235	094813	Profile 4	24.3 - 30.0 kft	139	
094420		Profile 4	26.0 kft	165	interrupt
094441		Profile 4	26.0 kft	196	resume
094813		Sonde 2	30.0 kft	313	end
094813	095602	Run 8	30.0 kft	317	
094942		Sonde 3	30.0 kft	322	
095634	100817	Profile 5	30.0 - 35.1 kft	359	
100817	101137	Run 9	35.1 kft	146	
101010		Sonde 4	35.0 kft	145	
101651	102630	Run 10	35.0 kft	317	
101707		Sonde 5	35.0 kft	320	
102036		ovhd jfj	35.0 kft	318	
102337		Sonde 6	35.0 kft	316	
103046	103657	Run 11	35.1 kft	114	
103703	105711	Profile 6	35.0 - 15.0 kft	146	
105908	110017	Orbit 3	15.1 - 15.0 kft	232	
110233	110250	Orbit 4	15.1 kft	352	
110301	110444	Orbit 5	15.1 kft	034	
110845	111106	Run 12	15.1 kft	149	
111454		Run 13	15.0 kft	332	
114130		Land	0.72 kft	157	Basel

B472 05:27:29-11:44:58

GLNG_PARA0581, GLAT_PARA0580

Sortie brief for FAAM

CAVIAR detachment 2009

Flight no:	B472
Proposed date:	Wednesday 29 July 2009
Prepared by:	Chawn Harlow
Version no.:	1.0, prepared 28 July 2009

Aim:	To sample intensively the water vapour structure of the atmosphere above the Jungfrauoch, and measure the radiative signature of the water vapour continuum.
Airfield:	Basel
Flight location:	Swiss Alps in vicinity of Jungfrauoch high altitude research station.
Weather conditions required:	Clear sky (or very nearly clear sky, preferably $\frac{1}{8}$ cloud or less) from surface to space.
Dropsondes:	6 required.

Further sortie details

Coordinates: aim to fly straight and level runs between fixed coordinates

BADEP = 47° 1.6' N, 7° 25.5' E

(Jungfrauoch = 46° 32.9' N, 7° 59.1' E)

A = 46° 22.0' N, 8° 10.0' E

The runs are of approx. 10 mins duration, may be slightly longer at the lowest altitudes.

Orientation: Track approx. 142°T and reciprocal over Jungfrauoch and neighbouring glacier.

Radiometers: ARIES and TAFTS to coordinate their upward and downward views during the straight and level runs. SWS to scan a range of angles except during orbits.

Note that the following flight altitudes are examples only, and in practice these will be chosen by the mission scientist.

Sortie profile

No.	Item	Time	Cumulative time
1	Take off from Basel at 0730Z (0930L)		
2	Transit to arrive at BADEP at FL280	00:25	00:25
3	Perform straight and level run (SLR) from BADEP to A at FL280, drop one sonde	00:15	00:40
4	Reposition from A to the Jungfrauoch	00:05	00:45
5	Perform two orbits with angle of bank greater than SZA	00:10	00:55
6	Perform spiral descent from FL280 to FL150 over the Jungfrauoch at 1000 ft/min	00:15	01:10
7	Reposition from Jungfrauoch to A	00:05	01:15
8	Perform SLR (A to BADEP) at FL150. Please maintain straight and level over glacier.	00:15	01:30
9	Climbing turn to FL190, rate of climb 1000 ft/min or less	00:05	01:35
10	Perform SLR (BADEP to A) at FL190	00:10	01:45
11	Climbing turn to FL240, rate of climb 1000 ft/min or less	00:05	01:50
12	Perform SLR (A to BADEP) at FL240	00:10	02:00
13	Climbing turn to FL300, rate of climb 1000 ft/min or less	00:10	02:10
14	Perform SLR (A to BADEP) at FL300, drop two sondes	00:10	02:20
15	Straight climb (BADEP to A) to FL350, rate of climb 1000 ft/min or less	00:20	02:40
16	Perform SLR (A to BADEP) at FL350, drop two sondes.	00:15	02:55
17	Procedural turn for reciprocal run	00:05	03:00
18	Reciprocal SLR (BADEP to A) at FL350, drop one sonde	00:10	03:10
19	Reposition from A to JFJ	00:05	03:15
20	Perform spiral descent from FL350 to FL150 over the Jungfrauoch at 1000 ft/min	00:20	03:35
21	Perform two orbits with angle of bank greater than SZA	00:10	03:45
22	Reposition from Jungfrauoch to A	00:05	03:50
23	Perform SLR (A to BADEP) at FL150. Please maintain straight and level over glacier.	00:15	04:05
24	Return to Basel	00:15	04:20

B472: Sortie Debrief

Campaign: CAVIAR

Mission Scientist: Chawn Harlow

Date: 29/07/09

This sortie entailed stacked runs along the line BADEP to A. The first run was carried out at FL280 with the release of one sonde. The run at FL280 was followed by two orbits with an angle of bank of 43° . A spiral descent was then carried out to FL150. Then stacked SLR's were carried out along the line BADEP to A at FL150, 190, 240, 300, and 350. Two sondes were dropped at FL300 and three at FL350. A spiral descent was then carried out to FL150 followed by two orbits at 60° and 43° angle of bank, respectively. Finally, an SLR from A to BADEP at FL150 was carried out on the way back to Basel. Repositions were carried out along the Jungfrauoch to A line giving multiple runs over the glacier at FL150, 280 and 350.

The entire sortie was carried out in cloud-free conditions. However, the sortie was plagued by a delay at FL150 due to air traffic. This allowed an extra run at FL150 over the glacier but shortened the run on the BADEP end.

ARIES was unserviceable during the bulk of the sortie. TAFTS had troubles during the run at FL350. Sonde 2 failed to deploy its chute.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B 472 Date 29/7/09 Name Chawn Harlow Page 1 of 3

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
07:35:30	T/O	860'			Take off Basel
	R1				Jungfrau region clear at all levels. SCu at very low level on Italian side
08:08:16	R1	FL280			Start R1
08:14:58	S1	"			Sonde 1
08:16:32	R1	"			End R1
08:21:30	R2	"			Start R2 Reposition to JFJ
08:23: ²⁵ 44	R2	"			
08: ^{23:44} 25:58	O1				Start O1
08:25:58	O1				End Orbit 1
08:26:27	O2				Start Orbit 2
08:28:33	O2				End Orbit 2
08:29:05	P1	FL280			R Start Profile 1 Spiral
08:42:22	P1	FL150			End Profile 1
08:44:09	R3	"			Start JFJ to A
08:46:26	R3	"			End
08:50:34	R4	"			Start Run 4 A to BADEP
08:57:44	R4				End
	R2	FL150			Start Profile 2 at BADEP
	R2				Delayed short of BADEP by ATC
9:14:17	R5	FL150			JFJ to A
9:15:17	R5	"			End
9:16:36	P2	FL150			Start Profile 2 at A
9:20:00	P2	FL190			End

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.472 Date 29/7/09 Name C. Harlow Page 2 of 3

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
09:20:00	R6	FL190	316		Start R6 A to BADEP
09:29:47	R6	"			End R6
09:30:02	P3	FL190			Start
09:34:56	P3	FL240			End at BADEP
09:34:57	R7	"	145		Start Run 7 BADEP to A
09:42:35	P4				
09:42:35	R7	"			End R7
09:42:35	P4	FL240			Start P4
09:48:24	P4	FL300			End P4
09:48:24 9:56:02	R8	"			Start Run 8 A to BADEP
09:56:02	R8	"			End Run 8
09:56:34	P5	FL300			Start Profile 5
10:08:17	P5	FL350			End Profile 5
09:48:24	S2	FL300			Sonde 2 - Fast fall
09:49:42	S3	FL300			Sonde 3
10:10:10	S4	FL350			Sonde 4 over JFJ
10:08:17	R9	"			Start Run 9 JFJ to A
10:11:37	R9	"			End Run 9
10:16:51	R10	"			Start Run 10 A to BADEP
10:17:08	S5	"			Sonde 5
10:23:36	S6	"			Sonde 6
10:26		"			2 DC seeing small ice particles
10:26:36	R10	"			End Run 10
10:30:46	R11	FL350			Start Run 11
10:36:57	R11	"			End Run 11

Cloud Physics Flight Log B472

Date:29/07/09	Operator:PDR	DRS Time:	DAU1 Time:	DAU2 Time:	AUX1 Time:	AUX2 Time:
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DAU2 Disk space? 1160 MB

	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		SID2			
Operated?	Y		Y		Y		Y		N			
Pre-flight checks	Ref V:	4.15	Vref (>7V):	7.4	Vref (>7):	2.3	El#1 V (>1):	2	Comms?:			
	Data TX?	Y	Sample flow	1.15	Flow (~1):	3.86	El#32 V (>1):	1.5				
			Sheath flow	14	Pressure:	1.38						
			Spectra ok?	Y	Temp (NDIT)	73.2						

Just after take-off	Are SAMPLE and RECORD buttons on PADS both green?	Y	Are all heaters on? (Check ammeters and CIP dummy box heater switch).	Y
	Are all PADS instruments enabled and updating?	Y		

NOTE that CTRL+T will insert the current time where the cursor is as long as the cursor is a cursor and not a selected box.

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	SID2	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R			
												Cal'd CDP with 30 micron beads (~05:50:40) and 15 micron beads (~05:51:40)
07:36:00												Heaters and hotwire lwc on
10:36:00	FI350											Particles seen by 2DC, however the images only show a single pixel generally on the far edge element so could be noise caused by arm misalignment in the cold
11:36:00												Heaters and hotwire off

Post flight

Instrument	Diagnostics		Brief report on instrument performance
PCASP (old)	Vref:		
	Flow:		
2DC	El#1:	1.6	Worked fine, see above for high altitude measurements
	El#32:	2.1	
PCASP SPP-200	Ref V:	7.5	Worked fine. Some noise at high altitude
	Flow:	1.16	
CDP	Laser V:	3.25	Worked fine
FFSSP	Ref V:		
SID 3	Laser V:		Not run
Rack Equipment			Please note SEADAS disk space remaining.

Flight:

B472

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problem

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nevzorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

HORACE:

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H (VIRC):

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

PCASP SPP-200:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP (fuselage):

CDP (Canister):

CIP 100 (PIP):

CIP 25 (CIP):

CPI:

CVI (Inlet):

CVI PCASP-X:

CVI Ly-A Hygro:

FSSP (UMan):

SID1:

SID2:

SID3:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC (AMS):

SMPS (AMS):

CPC 3010A (CVI):

INC:

Mini-LIDAR:

SP2:

UHSAS:

VACC:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR (big):

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B472

Date: 29/7/09

Instruments

1. RFC not operational
2. The MPDS system continues to not connect - "Error 678 Remote computer did not respond."
I've tried re-making the circuit breakers. The ISDN connection setup was not on the FM pc.
I've tried following instructions I found on the FM pc for setting one up, and the resulting connection comes up with the same error as the mpds. Suspect Swift64 system u/s.
- 3.

Aircraft

- 1.
- 2.
- 3.

Satcom-H Calls

nil

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

ARIES flight log

Flight: 8472

page 1 of 2

Date: 29/07/09 Operator(s): D. T. W. DEMAN

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: CAUIAN SWITZER LAND

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
							CN2
							Carrier Nadir 2 emit 30s (CH30s, N30s, Z30s) x00
							CZP
							Carrier Profile Zen (CH20s, Z20s) x00
0750ish							Temps etc + spectrum went wildly wrong - restart everything
060828	FL280	CN2		0	71	31	Seems ok for the moment!
081500	FL280	CN2		0	71	31	Stop script
082110	FL280	CN2		0	71	31	Start
082345	FL280	CN2		0	71	31	Stop
082550	Orbit FL280	CZP		0	71	31	Start
083000	Profile descent				71	25	A few weird moments in the States, data and CBB got colder ...
0832							Back to normal?
084222	FL150 End profile	CZP		0	71	30	
084470	FL150	CZP		0	71	31	Stop
084425	FL150	CN2		0	71	31	Start run
084655	FL150	CN2		0	71	30	Stop
085043	FL150	CN2		0	71	31	Start
085757	FL150	CN2		0	71	31	Stop
091417	FL150	CN2		0	71	31	Start (some odd temps at first)
091631	FL150	CN2		0	65	29	Odd temps BB
092000	FL190	CN2		0	71	30	
092476							Odd temps BB and Brightness temps
092933	FL190	CN2		0	-35 71	33	
0933							Tuned it all off - not helping

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	290709	Flight	B472	log pages
Operator(s)	JB	Campaign	CAVIAR			
Departure	Basel	Arrival	Basel			

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection						•
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						•
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						•
FERA on					at time	05:24
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	18°C	Ch	18°C	Ch18	18°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on					at time	05:25
Initial target temperatures	Hot	288	Cold	289		
Target heating						•
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						•
Scanning on (LMD box)					at time	test 05:51
Scan indication	Monitor			•	Visual	

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers						
Turn on Deimos CPU						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Start Deimos Software					at time	
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual		
Weather	Cloud		Precip			
	Surface		Pressure			
	Other					

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC} = t_{DRS} +$	0	at time	07:10:00		
Brightness temps 'sensible'						•
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344.6	Cold	303.2	
	Deimos:	Hot		Cold		
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B		
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)		
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20	
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)	
	36.58	30.73	39.47	42.85	42.01	

Power changeover

Headset on before start						•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.					•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)						•
Exit Deimos Software (x)						
POWER CHANGEOVER						
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton					•
Restart Deimos Software						
System running again					at time	

B472_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog

```

05:40:59.68 --- - - - -
05:40:59.68 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
05:40:59.68 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
                                tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
05:40:59.69 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B472
05:40:59.69 --- - - - -
05:41:07.62 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
05:41:09.89 SWS 0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
05:41:10.45 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope stopped.
05:41:16.83 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 0.000
05:41:19.27 SWS - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
05:41:22.84 USH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
05:41:26.83 LSH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
05:41:52.90 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS FAILED NIR FAILED
05:42:00.90 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS FAILED NIR FAILED
05:42:02.20 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS FAILED NIR OK
05:42:36.30 --- - - - -
05:42:36.31 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
05:42:36.31 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
                                tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
05:42:36.31 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B472
05:42:36.31 --- - - - -
05:42:40.11 SWS - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
05:42:44.39 USH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
05:42:47.76 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
05:42:48.83 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
05:42:50.51 LSH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
05:42:52.10 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
05:42:55.23 SWS - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
05:42:56.65 SWS - - 40 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
05:42:56.66 SWS - - - 40 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
05:42:59.87 USH - - - 5 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
05:43:01.66 USH - - 40 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
05:43:01.66 USH - - - 40 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
05:43:04.55 LSH - - - 5 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
05:43:06.91 LSH - - 40 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
05:43:06.91 LSH - - - 40 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
05:43:09.24 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
05:43:09.24 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
05:43:09.24 SWS - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
05:43:13.80 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
05:43:17.94 SWS - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
05:43:17.96 LSH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
05:43:17.98 USH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
05:43:18.83 SWS - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
05:43:19.05 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
05:43:19.27 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
05:43:38.92 LSH - - - - Idling
05:43:38.92 SWS - - - - Idling
05:43:39.02 USH - - - - Idling
06:02:19.73 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
06:02:19.73 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
06:02:19.74 SWS - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
06:02:22.63 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
06:02:26.08 SWS - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
06:02:26.19 USH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
06:02:26.21 LSH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
06:02:27.44 SWS - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
06:02:27.92 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
06:02:28.18 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
06:02:29.37 LSH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
06:02:29.43 SWS - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
06:02:29.47 USH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
06:02:30.94 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
06:02:31.09 SWS - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
06:02:31.26 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
06:02:42.28 --- - - - - *** microtops comparison

```

```

06:07:27.77 --- - - - - *** end of microtops compariosn
06:07:30.88 SWS - - - - Idling
06:07:30.96 USH - - - - Idling
06:07:30.97 LSH - - - - Idling
06:07:33.23 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
06:07:37.35 USH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
06:07:37.35 SWS - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
06:07:37.51 LSH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
06:07:38.28 LSH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
06:07:39.02 USH - - - - Idling
06:07:39.20 SWS - - - - Idling
06:07:40.02 LSH - - - - Idling
06:07:41.11 SWS - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
06:07:41.12 LSH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
06:07:41.12 USH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
06:07:43.13 SWS - - - - Idling
06:07:43.25 LSH - - - - Idling
06:07:43.28 USH - - - - Idling
06:07:45.87 SWS - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
06:07:45.87 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
06:07:45.91 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
06:07:46.81 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
06:07:46.94 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
06:07:48.99 USH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
06:07:48.99 LSH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
06:07:49.02 SWS - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
06:07:50.84 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
06:07:50.99 SWS - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
06:07:51.11 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
06:07:52.11 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
06:07:54.28 SWS - - - - Idling
06:07:54.32 USH - - - - Idling
06:07:54.32 LSH - - - - Idling
07:03:35.06 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
07:03:35.06 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
07:03:35.08 SWS - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
07:03:37.16 SWS - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
07:03:38.03 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
07:03:44.15 SWS - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
07:03:44.15 USH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
07:03:44.21 LSH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
07:03:45.47 SWS - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
07:03:46.16 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
07:03:46.28 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
07:03:48.18 USH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
07:03:48.30 LSH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
07:03:48.30 SWS - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
07:03:49.59 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
07:03:50.17 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
07:03:50.28 SWS - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
07:03:52.24 USH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
07:03:52.29 SWS - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
07:03:52.32 LSH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
07:03:53.68 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
07:03:54.22 SWS - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
07:03:54.33 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
07:03:55.24 SWS - - - - Idling
07:03:55.24 USH - - - - Idling
07:03:55.31 LSH - - - - Idling
07:07:58.12 SWS - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
07:07:58.13 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
07:07:58.15 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
07:07:59.35 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
07:07:59.40 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
07:08:01.88 SWS - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
07:08:01.91 USH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
07:08:01.94 LSH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
07:08:03.24 SWS - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
07:08:03.75 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.

```

07:08:03.95	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:08:04.88	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:08:04.98	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:08:04.98	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:08:06.28	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:08:06.40	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:08:07.09	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:36:30.48	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
07:36:35.36	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:36:35.44	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:36:35.45	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:36:35.84	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:36:36.04	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:36:36.21	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:36:36.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:36:37.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:36:37.90	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:36:37.92	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:36:38.02	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:36:38.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:36:39.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:36:39.21	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:36:40.37	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:36:40.37	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:45:47.54	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:45:47.54	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:45:47.55	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:45:48.38	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:45:48.68	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:45:48.88	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:45:50.35	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:45:50.37	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:45:50.47	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:45:50.83	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:45:51.03	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:45:51.20	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:45:51.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:45:52.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:45:53.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:45:54.98	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:45:54.98	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:45:54.99	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:49:41.64	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
07:49:45.53	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:49:45.58	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:49:45.62	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:49:45.80	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:49:46.63	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:49:46.86	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:49:47.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:49:48.15	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:49:48.23	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:49:48.25	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:49:48.82	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:49:49.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:49:49.20	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:49:49.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:49:51.24	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:49:51.25	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:57:56.55	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:57:56.61	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:57:56.62	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:57:57.40	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:57:57.68	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:57:57.89	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:57:59.00	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:57:59.01	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:57:59.07	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
07:57:59.89	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.

07:58:00.13	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:58:00.25	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
07:58:11.22	---	-	-	-	-	*** clear skies above
08:00:57.26	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:00:57.31	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:00:57.33	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:00:58.16	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:00:58.38	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:00:58.65	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:01:45.73	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:01:45.78	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:01:45.81	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:01:46.58	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:01:46.83	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:01:47.05	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:02:48.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope motor initialised.
08:08:16.10	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 1 at FL 280 BADEP to A
08:08:16.64	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.000
08:08:20.61	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:08:25.07	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
08:08:28.67	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:08:29.72	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:08:29.74	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:08:29.74	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:08:30.61	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:08:30.83	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:08:31.14	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:08:36.77	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:08:44.85	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:08:52.91	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:09:00.96	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:09:09.02	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:09:17.10	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:09:25.24	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:09:33.29	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:09:41.32	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:09:49.34	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:09:57.39	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:10:05.43	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:10:13.45	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:10:21.48	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:10:29.51	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:10:37.54	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:10:45.60	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:10:53.61	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:11:01.67	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:11:09.77	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:11:17.82	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:11:25.85	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:11:33.87	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:11:41.87	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:11:49.82	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:11:57.85	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:12:05.91	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:12:14.08	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:12:22.04	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:12:30.06	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:12:38.18	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:12:46.18	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:12:54.23	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:13:02.28	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:13:10.32	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:13:18.42	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:13:26.50	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:13:34.55	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:13:42.62	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:13:50.72	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:13:58.85	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:14:06.94	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0

```

08:14:15.02 SWS -45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:14:23.09 SWS 45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:14:31.18 SWS -45.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:14:39.32 SWS 45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:14:47.39 SWS -45.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:14:55.42 SWS 45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:15:03.51 SWS -45.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:15:11.60 SWS 45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:15:19.73 SWS -45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:15:27.75 SWS 45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:15:35.85 SWS -45.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:15:43.89 SWS 45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:15:50.50 --- - - - *** over glacier
08:15:51.86 SWS -45.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:15:59.90 SWS 45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:16:07.89 SWS -45.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:16:15.99 SWS 45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:16:24.04 SWS -45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:16:32.08 SWS 45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:16:40.11 SWS -45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:16:43.13 --- - - - *** end of run
08:16:46.77 SWS 30.5 - - - Telescope stopped.
08:16:54.51 SWS 30.5 - - - Telescope sent to 0.000
08:17:04.50 LSH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
08:17:04.59 USH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
08:17:04.62 SWS - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
08:17:05.37 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
08:17:05.63 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
08:17:05.85 SWS - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
08:20:53.45 SWS - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
08:20:53.52 LSH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
08:20:53.52 USH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
08:20:54.38 SWS - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
08:20:54.59 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
08:20:54.82 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
08:21:58.78 --- - - - 
08:21:58.78 --- - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
08:21:58.78 --- - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
                    tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
08:21:58.78 --- - - - +++ Flight no. B472
08:21:58.78 --- - - - 
08:22:00.71 SWS - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
08:22:04.15 USH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
08:22:06.90 LSH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
08:22:09.98 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
08:22:10.07 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
08:22:10.25 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
08:22:16.65 SWS - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
08:22:18.84 SWS - - 40 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
08:22:18.85 SWS - - - 40 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
08:22:19.57 SWS - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
08:22:20.75 USH - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
08:22:22.70 USH - - 40 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
08:22:22.70 USH - - - 40 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
08:22:23.42 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
08:22:25.69 LSH - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
08:22:27.33 LSH - - 40 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
08:22:27.33 LSH - - - 40 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
08:22:28.11 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
08:22:31.24 --- - - - Reset shutters.
08:22:34.49 LSH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
08:22:34.51 SWS - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
08:22:34.51 USH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
08:22:35.33 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
08:22:35.55 SWS - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
08:22:35.78 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
08:22:37.69 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
08:22:40.84 SWS 0.0 - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
08:23:00.13 --- - - - *** SWS NIR module dropped out,

```

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08:23:15.95 --- - - - - *** restarted software al looks ok again now
08:23:20.31 SWS - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
08:23:20.37 USH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
08:23:20.40 LSH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
08:23:20.98 LSH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
08:23:21.15 SWS - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
08:23:21.40 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
08:23:21.91 LSH - - - - Idling
08:23:23.81 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
08:23:32.08 SWS -6.0 - - - Telescope sent to 0.000
08:23:46.29 --- - - - - *** orbit 1 40 deg to the right
08:25:59.97 --- - - - - *** end of orbit
08:26:20.09 SWS - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
08:26:29.07 --- - - - - *** orbit 2 to the right 40 deg
08:28:31.25 SWS - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
08:28:34.88 --- - - - - *** end of orbit
08:28:39.82 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
08:28:43.22 LSH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
08:28:43.25 USH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
08:28:43.26 SWS - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
08:28:44.11 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
08:28:44.37 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
08:28:44.46 SWS - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
08:28:45.59 LSH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
08:28:45.60 USH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
08:28:45.69 SWS - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
08:28:46.27 SWS - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
08:28:46.45 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
08:28:46.70 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
08:28:47.14 SWS - - - - Idling
08:28:54.79 SWS - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
08:29:09.62 --- - - - - *** profile descent
08:29:18.73 --- - - - - *** spiral (profile 1)
08:29:22.41 USH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
08:29:22.47 LSH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
08:29:22.49 SWS - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
08:29:23.09 SWS - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
08:29:23.32 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
08:29:23.47 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
08:29:23.96 SWS - - - - Idling
08:29:26.14 SWS - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
08:39:32.34 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
08:39:35.59 USH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
08:39:36.43 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
08:42:20.43 --- - - - - *** end of profile descent at FL 150
08:42:22.82 SWS - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
08:42:22.84 USH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
08:42:22.90 LSH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
08:42:23.67 SWS - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
08:42:23.97 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
08:42:24.16 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
08:44:12.25 SWS -0.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:44:12.67 SWS 1.8 - - - Telescope sent to -45.000
08:44:16.58 SWS 41.4 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:44:17.25 SWS 33.3 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:44:17.94 SWS 25.2 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:44:18.64 SWS 16.7 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:44:19.33 SWS 8.4 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:44:20.05 SWS -0.2 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:44:20.72 SWS -8.7 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:44:21.43 SWS -16.6 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:44:22.13 SWS -25.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:44:22.82 SWS -33.7 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:44:23.53 SWS -41.9 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:44:24.25 SWS -45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:44:32.16 SWS 45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:44:33.00 --- - - - - *** run from JFR to A
08:44:40.03 SWS -45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:44:47.93 SWS 45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0

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08:44:55.84 SWS -45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:45:03.70 SWS 45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:45:06.30 --- - - - *** run 3
08:45:11.59 SWS -45.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:45:19.48 SWS 45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:45:27.38 SWS -45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:45:35.29 SWS 45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:45:43.14 SWS -45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:45:51.04 SWS 45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:45:59.04 SWS -45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:46:06.94 SWS 45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:46:14.83 SWS -45.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:46:22.73 SWS 45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:46:28.13 SWS -15.5 - - - Telescope stopped.
08:46:35.64 SWS -15.5 - - - Telescope sent to 0.000
08:46:47.98 --- - - - *** end of run 3 08.40.26
08:47:02.24 --- - - - *** correction 08:46:26
08:47:08.64 USH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
08:47:08.66 LSH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
08:47:08.79 SWS - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
08:47:09.50 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
08:47:09.74 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
08:47:09.95 SWS - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
08:47:11.23 LSH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
08:47:11.25 USH - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
08:47:11.28 SWS - - 40 40 Dark measurement started.
08:47:12.14 LSH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
08:47:12.33 USH - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
08:47:12.48 SWS - - 40 40 Manual scene recording started.
08:47:44.16 --- - - - *** start of run from A to BADEP at FL 150
08:48:50.22 --- - - - *** correction start of run now
08:50:34.10 --- - - - *** actual start of run now
08:50:41.92 SWS -0.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:50:42.33 SWS 1.8 - - - Telescope sent to -45.000
08:50:46.26 SWS 41.3 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:50:46.94 SWS 33.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:50:47.66 SWS 24.5 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:50:48.35 SWS 16.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:50:49.07 SWS 7.5 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:50:49.78 SWS -0.9 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:50:50.51 SWS -9.5 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:50:51.22 SWS -18.2 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:50:51.93 SWS -26.7 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:50:52.64 SWS -35.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:50:53.34 SWS -43.5 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:51:01.23 SWS 45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:51:09.17 SWS -45.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:51:17.05 SWS 45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:51:24.96 SWS -45.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:51:32.85 SWS 45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:51:40.74 SWS -45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:51:48.62 SWS 45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:51:56.48 SWS -45.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:52:04.42 SWS 45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:52:12.28 SWS -45.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:52:20.17 SWS 45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:52:28.06 SWS -45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:52:35.96 SWS 45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:52:43.84 SWS -45.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:52:51.72 SWS 45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:52:59.61 SWS -45.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:53:07.52 SWS 45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:53:15.40 SWS -45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:53:23.41 SWS 45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:53:31.33 SWS -45.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:53:39.17 SWS 45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:53:47.06 SWS -45.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:53:54.94 SWS 45.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:54:02.85 SWS -45.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0

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08:54:10.75	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:54:18.60	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:54:26.50	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:54:34.42	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:54:42.29	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:54:50.19	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:54:58.09	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:55:06.05	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:55:13.94	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:55:21.81	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:55:29.73	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:55:37.63	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:55:45.50	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:55:53.40	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:56:01.29	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:56:09.17	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:56:17.06	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:56:22.35	---	-	-	-	-	***
08:56:22.40	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:56:22.42	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:56:22.43	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:56:23.28	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:56:23.44	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:56:23.67	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:56:25.11	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:56:26.68	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:56:26.70	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:56:26.75	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
08:56:27.53	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:56:27.75	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:56:27.96	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
08:56:32.94	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:56:40.86	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:56:48.73	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:56:56.63	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:57:04.52	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:57:12.38	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:57:20.33	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:57:28.24	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:57:36.19	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
08:57:44.06	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
08:57:47.83	SWS	-4.1	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
09:01:07.50	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:01:07.50	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:01:07.55	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:01:08.37	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:01:08.59	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:01:08.84	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:01:09.67	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:01:09.69	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:01:09.84	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:01:10.52	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:01:10.75	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:01:10.96	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:01:16.61	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:01:16.65	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:01:16.68	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:01:17.47	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:01:17.75	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:01:17.98	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:01:20.69	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:01:20.71	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:01:20.76	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:01:21.53	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:01:21.77	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:01:21.98	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:09:04.92	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:09:04.93	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:09:04.99	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.

09:09:05.60	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:09:05.83	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:09:06.04	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:09:06.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:09:07.26	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:09:07.28	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:09:07.35	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:09:08.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:09:08.37	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:09:08.54	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:09:08.87	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:09:08.91	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:09:08.96	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:09:09.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:09:09.99	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:09:10.19	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:09:10.91	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:14:20.24	---	-	-	-	-	*** run from JFJ to A
09:14:20.65	SWS	-4.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.000
09:14:24.61	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:14:32.54	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:14:40.44	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:14:48.42	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:14:56.34	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:15:04.28	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:15:12.31	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:15:20.22	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:15:28.13	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:15:36.02	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:15:43.98	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:15:51.89	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:15:59.76	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:16:07.66	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:16:15.54	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:16:18.77	SWS	-10.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
09:16:26.41	SWS	-10.7	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
09:16:36.66	---	-	-	-	-	*** ascent to FL 190
09:16:40.62	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:16:40.71	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:16:40.78	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:16:41.29	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:16:41.47	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:16:41.70	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:16:42.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:16:42.89	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:16:42.91	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:16:42.99	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:16:43.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:16:44.00	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:16:44.22	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:16:45.46	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:18:13.10	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:18:13.16	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:18:13.19	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:18:14.02	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:18:14.22	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:18:14.41	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:18:16.48	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:18:16.55	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:18:16.58	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:18:17.15	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:18:17.36	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:18:17.54	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:18:18.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:18:20.40	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:20:01.15	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 5 from A to BADEP at FL 190
09:20:01.43	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:20:01.87	SWS	1.9	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.000
09:20:05.76	SWS	41.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0

09:20:06.43	SWS	33.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:20:07.16	SWS	24.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:20:07.87	SWS	16.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:20:08.58	SWS	7.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:20:09.30	SWS	-1.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:20:10.03	SWS	-9.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:20:10.80	SWS	-18.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:20:11.51	SWS	-27.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:20:12.24	SWS	-36.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:20:12.99	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:20:17.16	---	-	-	-	-	*** correction run 6
09:20:20.88	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:20:28.77	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:20:36.78	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:20:44.70	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:20:52.67	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:21:00.59	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:21:03.63	---	-	-	-	-	*** stray reflec between 25 and 45 deg
09:21:08.59	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:21:16.59	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:21:24.49	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:21:33.04	SWS	-54.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 25.0
09:21:40.35	SWS	25.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:21:47.73	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 20.0
09:21:54.61	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:22:01.46	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 20.0
09:22:08.37	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:22:15.23	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 20.0
09:22:22.11	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:22:29.02	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 20.0
09:22:35.81	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:22:42.56	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 20.0
09:22:49.34	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:22:56.13	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 20.0
09:23:03.05	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:23:09.91	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 20.0
09:23:16.79	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:23:23.57	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 20.0
09:23:30.38	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:23:37.25	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 20.0
09:23:44.11	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:23:50.92	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 20.0
09:23:57.80	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:24:04.61	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 20.0
09:24:11.46	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:24:18.28	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 20.0
09:24:25.15	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:24:31.91	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 20.0
09:24:38.71	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:24:45.60	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 20.0
09:24:52.36	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:24:59.18	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 20.0
09:25:06.05	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:25:12.90	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 20.0
09:25:19.73	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:25:26.57	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 20.0
09:25:33.34	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:25:40.23	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 20.0
09:25:47.07	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:25:54.02	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 20.0
09:26:00.79	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:26:07.64	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 20.0
09:26:14.51	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:26:21.37	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 20.0
09:26:28.24	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:26:35.05	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 20.0
09:26:41.91	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:26:47.61	SWS	-44.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 20.0
09:26:53.39	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0

09:26:59.14	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 20.0
09:27:04.83	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:27:10.58	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 20.0
09:27:16.32	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:27:22.13	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 20.0
09:27:27.85	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:27:33.58	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 20.0
09:27:39.62	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:27:45.37	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 20.0
09:27:51.07	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:27:56.80	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 20.0
09:28:02.50	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:28:08.45	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 20.0
09:28:14.42	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:28:19.67	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
09:28:20.15	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 20.0
09:28:23.61	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:28:23.64	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:28:23.64	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:28:24.46	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:28:24.71	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:28:24.96	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:28:25.87	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:28:26.70	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:28:26.72	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:28:26.73	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:28:27.56	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:28:27.84	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:28:28.05	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:28:31.57	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 20.0
09:28:37.29	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:28:43.14	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 20.0
09:28:48.93	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:28:54.73	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 20.0
09:29:00.53	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:29:06.31	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 20.0
09:29:12.09	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:29:17.83	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 20.0
09:29:23.48	SWS	19.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:29:29.25	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 20.0
09:29:34.94	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:29:40.65	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 20.0
09:29:43.63	---	-	-	-	-	*** very dry at this end of run and high ozone
09:29:46.37	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:29:49.58	SWS	-14.2	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
09:30:07.65	SWS	-14.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
09:30:12.75	---	-	-	-	-	*** ozone at 80 ppb
09:30:17.07	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb
09:30:19.87	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:30:19.90	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:30:19.98	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:30:20.84	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:30:21.07	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:30:21.22	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:30:59.28	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:30:59.30	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:30:59.36	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:31:00.16	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:31:00.34	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:31:00.57	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:32:22.32	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:32:22.33	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:32:22.38	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:32:23.00	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:32:23.24	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:32:23.42	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:32:23.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:32:24.85	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:32:24.89	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.

09:32:24.96	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:32:25.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:32:25.98	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:32:26.19	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:32:26.96	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:32:27.01	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:32:27.06	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:32:27.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:32:28.03	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:32:28.32	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:32:28.65	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:32:29.62	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:32:50.22	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:32:50.30	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:32:50.31	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:32:51.12	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:32:51.30	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:32:51.53	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:32:52.45	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:32:52.50	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:32:52.53	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:32:53.37	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:32:53.55	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:32:53.74	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:33:08.40	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:33:08.46	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:33:08.47	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:33:09.31	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:33:09.52	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:33:09.68	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:34:54.82	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.000
09:34:57.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:34:58.72	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 20.0
09:35:03.09	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at FL 240
09:35:04.52	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:35:09.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:35:10.28	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 20.0
09:35:15.96	SWS	20.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:35:20.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:35:21.72	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:35:29.73	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
09:35:35.98	SWS	-25.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:35:42.30	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
09:35:48.52	SWS	-25.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:35:54.85	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
09:36:01.19	SWS	-25.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:36:07.52	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
09:36:13.86	SWS	-25.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:36:20.19	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
09:36:26.53	SWS	-25.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:36:32.86	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
09:36:39.15	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:36:45.50	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
09:36:51.85	SWS	-25.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:36:58.18	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
09:37:04.38	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:37:10.62	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
09:37:16.87	SWS	-25.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:37:23.18	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
09:37:29.43	SWS	-25.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:37:35.74	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
09:37:42.09	SWS	-25.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:37:48.42	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
09:37:54.71	SWS	-25.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:38:00.96	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
09:38:07.30	SWS	-25.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:38:13.63	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
09:38:19.81	SWS	-25.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:38:26.05	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0

09:38:32.33	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:38:38.64	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
09:38:44.85	SWS	-25.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:38:51.18	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
09:38:57.53	SWS	-25.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:39:03.85	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
09:39:10.17	SWS	-25.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:39:16.52	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
09:39:22.87	SWS	-25.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:39:29.24	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
09:39:35.59	SWS	-25.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:39:41.86	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
09:39:48.23	SWS	-25.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:39:54.52	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
09:40:00.86	SWS	-25.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:40:07.18	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
09:40:13.49	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:40:19.95	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
09:40:26.28	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:40:32.77	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
09:40:36.34	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:40:36.35	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:40:36.40	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:40:37.27	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:40:37.47	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:40:37.64	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:40:38.61	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:40:38.63	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:40:38.66	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:40:39.06	SWS	-25.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:40:39.31	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:40:39.49	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:40:39.72	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:40:40.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:40:41.54	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:40:45.33	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
09:40:51.65	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:40:57.96	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
09:41:04.28	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:41:10.60	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
09:41:16.88	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:41:23.23	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
09:41:29.60	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:41:35.95	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
09:41:42.28	SWS	-25.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:41:48.62	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
09:41:54.95	SWS	-25.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:42:01.29	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
09:42:06.21	SWS	-10.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
09:42:13.25	SWS	-9.9	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
09:44:51.86	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb
09:44:56.28	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:44:56.29	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:44:56.32	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:44:57.27	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:44:57.43	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:44:57.58	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:45:00.89	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:45:00.91	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:45:00.98	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:45:01.75	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:45:01.98	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:45:02.20	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:48:14.66	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 8 at FL 300 from A to BADEP
09:48:15.09	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:48:15.50	SWS	1.9	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.000
09:48:17.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:48:19.46	SWS	40.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:48:20.14	SWS	32.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0

09:48:20.87	SWS	24.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:48:21.60	SWS	15.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:48:22.31	SWS	6.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:48:23.10	SWS	-2.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:48:23.81	SWS	-11.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:48:24.60	SWS	-20.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:48:25.32	SWS	-29.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:48:26.07	SWS	-38.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:48:26.80	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:48:32.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:48:34.77	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:48:42.73	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:48:48.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:48:50.65	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:48:58.50	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:49:04.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:49:06.45	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:49:14.57	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:49:20.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:49:22.59	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:49:23.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:49:30.63	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
09:49:36.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:49:38.63	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:49:46.65	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 25.0
09:49:52.98	SWS	25.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:49:59.30	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 25.0
09:50:05.64	SWS	25.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:50:11.90	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 25.0
09:50:18.23	SWS	25.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:50:24.59	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 25.0
09:50:30.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:50:30.87	SWS	25.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:50:37.17	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 25.0
09:50:37.40	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:50:37.40	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:50:37.42	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:50:38.26	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:50:38.50	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:50:38.71	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:50:42.29	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:50:42.31	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:50:42.33	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:50:43.17	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:50:43.40	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:50:43.58	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:50:43.62	SWS	25.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:50:49.87	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
09:50:55.08	SWS	14.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:51:00.85	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
09:51:06.54	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:51:11.79	SWS	-44.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
09:51:17.02	SWS	14.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:51:22.22	SWS	-44.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
09:51:27.43	SWS	14.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:51:32.62	SWS	-44.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
09:51:37.79	SWS	13.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:51:43.04	SWS	-44.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
09:51:48.22	SWS	13.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:51:53.94	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
09:51:59.18	SWS	14.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:52:04.38	SWS	-43.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
09:52:09.59	SWS	14.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:52:14.92	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
09:52:20.13	SWS	14.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:52:25.34	SWS	-44.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
09:52:31.00	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:52:36.23	SWS	-44.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
09:52:41.96	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0

09:52:47.17	SWS	-44.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
09:52:52.35	SWS	13.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:52:57.62	SWS	-44.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
09:53:02.81	SWS	14.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:53:08.07	SWS	-44.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
09:53:13.29	SWS	14.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:53:18.53	SWS	-44.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
09:53:23.74	SWS	14.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:53:28.99	SWS	-44.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
09:53:34.21	SWS	14.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:53:39.39	SWS	-44.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
09:53:44.63	SWS	14.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:53:49.85	SWS	-44.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
09:53:55.07	SWS	14.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:54:00.28	SWS	-44.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
09:54:06.01	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:54:11.20	SWS	-44.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
09:54:16.42	SWS	14.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:54:21.64	SWS	-44.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
09:54:26.84	SWS	14.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:54:32.56	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
09:54:37.77	SWS	14.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:54:42.98	SWS	-44.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
09:54:48.19	SWS	14.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:54:53.88	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
09:54:59.18	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:55:04.44	SWS	-44.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
09:55:09.76	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:55:14.98	SWS	-44.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
09:55:20.25	SWS	14.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:55:25.98	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
09:55:31.21	SWS	14.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
09:55:36.44	SWS	-44.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
09:55:41.39	SWS	10.3	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
09:55:42.91	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:55:42.94	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:55:42.97	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:55:43.78	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:55:44.09	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:55:44.26	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:55:44.79	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:55:44.94	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:55:44.96	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:55:45.65	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:55:46.02	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:55:46.16	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:55:51.86	SWS	10.3	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
09:55:53.02	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:55:53.06	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:55:53.07	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:55:53.50	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:55:53.71	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:55:53.88	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:55:54.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:55:54.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:55:55.54	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:55:55.55	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:55:55.59	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
09:55:56.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:55:56.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:55:56.88	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:55:57.33	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:55:57.33	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
09:56:36.00	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb
10:00:27.96	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:00:32.48	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:00:32.51	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:00:32.54	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:00:33.21	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.

10:00:33.42	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:00:33.59	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:00:34.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:00:34.95	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:00:34.97	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:00:35.02	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:00:35.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:00:36.10	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:00:36.31	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:00:36.91	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:06:26.20	---	-	-	-	-	***
10:06:26.29	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:06:26.30	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:06:26.34	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:06:26.98	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:06:27.17	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:06:27.42	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:06:27.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:06:28.42	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:06:28.52	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:06:28.55	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:06:29.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:06:29.54	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:06:29.73	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:06:30.96	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:08:15.44	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at FL 350
10:08:15.92	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.000
10:08:18.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:08:19.91	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:08:27.99	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
10:08:34.32	SWS	-25.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:08:40.66	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
10:08:47.02	SWS	-25.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:08:53.45	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
10:08:59.78	SWS	-25.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:09:06.19	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
10:09:12.57	SWS	-25.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:09:19.00	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
10:09:25.37	SWS	-25.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:09:31.68	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
10:09:38.00	SWS	-25.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:09:44.36	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
10:09:50.75	SWS	-25.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:09:57.11	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
10:10:03.45	SWS	-25.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:10:09.88	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
10:10:16.24	SWS	-25.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:10:22.58	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
10:10:28.96	SWS	-25.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:10:35.36	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
10:10:41.73	SWS	-25.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:10:48.11	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
10:10:54.46	SWS	-25.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:11:00.80	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
10:11:07.16	SWS	-25.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:11:13.57	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
10:11:20.00	SWS	-25.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:11:26.38	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
10:11:32.74	SWS	-25.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:11:39.14	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
10:11:39.80	SWS	41.2	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:11:45.82	SWS	41.3	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
10:11:48.96	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:11:48.98	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:11:48.99	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:11:49.83	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:11:50.12	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:11:50.36	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:11:51.67	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.

10:11:51.72	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:11:51.75	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:11:52.55	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:11:52.79	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:11:52.98	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:11:55.28	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:11:55.28	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:11:55.33	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:11:56.17	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:11:56.40	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:11:56.54	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:11:59.13	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:11:59.16	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:11:59.21	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:11:59.80	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:11:59.98	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:12:00.22	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:12:00.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:12:03.10	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:12:33.16	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:12:33.17	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:12:33.20	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:12:34.04	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:12:34.26	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:12:34.50	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:12:36.70	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:12:36.74	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:12:36.81	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:12:37.57	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:12:37.79	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:12:38.06	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:16:52.02	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:16:52.46	SWS	1.9	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.000
10:16:54.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:16:56.48	SWS	40.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:16:57.16	SWS	31.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:16:57.90	SWS	23.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:16:58.63	SWS	14.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:16:59.35	SWS	5.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:17:00.09	SWS	-3.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:17:00.82	SWS	-11.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:17:01.54	SWS	-20.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:17:02.28	SWS	-29.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:17:03.04	SWS	-38.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:17:03.76	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:17:09.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:17:10.08	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:17:10.09	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:17:10.21	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:17:10.98	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:17:11.25	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:17:11.47	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:17:11.94	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:17:13.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:17:13.35	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:17:13.37	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:17:13.40	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:17:14.05	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:17:14.27	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:17:14.51	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:17:15.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:17:17.38	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:17:20.00	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 25.0
10:17:25.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:17:26.37	SWS	25.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:17:32.75	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 25.0
10:17:38.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:17:39.10	SWS	25.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:17:45.53	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0

10:17:50.75	SWS	14.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:17:55.08	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 10 at FL 350
10:17:56.04	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:18:01.29	SWS	14.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:18:06.49	SWS	-44.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:18:11.73	SWS	14.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:18:16.94	SWS	-44.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:18:22.12	SWS	13.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:18:27.36	SWS	-44.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:18:32.63	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:18:37.89	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:18:43.13	SWS	14.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:18:48.47	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:18:53.67	SWS	13.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:18:58.97	SWS	-44.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:19:04.19	SWS	14.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:19:09.51	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:19:14.79	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:19:20.11	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:19:25.31	SWS	14.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:19:30.58	SWS	-44.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:19:35.83	SWS	14.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:19:41.09	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:19:46.32	SWS	14.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:19:51.58	SWS	-44.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:19:56.84	SWS	14.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:20:02.17	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:20:07.43	SWS	14.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:20:12.65	SWS	-44.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:20:17.93	SWS	14.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:20:23.16	SWS	-44.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:20:28.40	SWS	14.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:20:33.68	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:20:38.95	SWS	14.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:20:44.23	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:20:49.96	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:20:55.17	SWS	-44.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:21:00.38	SWS	14.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:21:05.59	SWS	-44.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:21:10.89	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:21:16.12	SWS	-44.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:21:21.37	SWS	14.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:21:26.63	SWS	-44.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:21:31.84	SWS	14.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:21:37.10	SWS	-44.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:21:42.37	SWS	14.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:21:48.10	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:21:51.92	---	-	-	-	-	*** going from A to BADEP
10:21:53.38	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:21:58.67	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:22:03.91	SWS	14.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:22:09.12	SWS	-44.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:22:14.39	SWS	14.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:22:19.59	SWS	-44.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:22:24.82	SWS	14.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:22:30.13	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:22:35.39	SWS	14.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:22:40.63	SWS	-44.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:22:45.91	SWS	14.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:22:51.21	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:22:56.50	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:23:01.74	SWS	-44.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:23:06.95	SWS	14.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:23:12.23	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:23:17.50	SWS	14.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:23:22.80	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:23:28.55	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:23:33.74	SWS	-43.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:23:39.00	SWS	14.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0

10:23:44.25	SWS	-44.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:23:49.49	SWS	14.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:23:54.75	SWS	-44.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:23:59.98	SWS	14.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:24:05.21	SWS	-44.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:24:10.44	SWS	14.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:24:15.71	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:24:20.96	SWS	14.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:24:26.00	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:24:26.09	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:24:26.09	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:24:26.13	SWS	-44.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:24:26.93	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:24:27.13	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:24:27.37	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:24:28.71	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:24:28.75	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:24:28.79	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:24:29.40	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:24:29.59	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:24:29.82	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:24:30.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:24:31.44	SWS	15.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:24:36.68	SWS	-44.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:24:41.92	SWS	14.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:24:47.59	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:24:52.77	SWS	13.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:24:58.02	SWS	-44.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:25:03.27	SWS	14.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:25:08.50	SWS	-44.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:25:13.73	SWS	14.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:25:18.99	SWS	-44.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:25:24.17	SWS	13.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:25:29.39	SWS	-44.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:25:34.60	SWS	14.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:25:39.82	SWS	-44.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:25:45.04	SWS	14.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:25:50.29	SWS	-44.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:25:55.52	SWS	14.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:26:00.70	SWS	-43.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:26:05.96	SWS	14.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:26:11.15	SWS	-44.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:26:16.39	SWS	14.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:26:21.64	SWS	-44.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:26:26.92	SWS	14.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:26:32.15	SWS	-44.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 15.0
10:26:37.13	SWS	10.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:26:43.09	SWS	10.9	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
10:26:49.08	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:26:49.10	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:26:49.20	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:26:49.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:26:50.15	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:26:50.41	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:26:52.65	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:26:52.67	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:26:52.73	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:26:53.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:26:53.73	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:26:53.98	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:26:55.35	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:26:55.35	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:26:55.46	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:26:56.19	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:26:56.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:26:56.62	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:27:00.88	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:28:34.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:30:46.76	---	-	-	-	-	*** run from BADEP to A at FL 350

10:30:47.33	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.000
10:30:51.37	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:30:59.50	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:30:59.98	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 11
10:31:07.57	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:31:08.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:31:15.71	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
10:31:22.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:31:22.12	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:31:22.15	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:31:22.16	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:31:23.04	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:31:23.26	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:31:23.48	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:31:23.85	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:31:24.14	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:31:24.14	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:31:24.23	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:31:25.04	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:31:25.24	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:31:25.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:31:25.48	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:31:26.45	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:31:26.50	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:31:26.52	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:31:27.12	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:31:27.36	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:31:27.58	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:31:28.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:31:28.98	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:31:29.01	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:31:29.02	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:31:29.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:31:30.07	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:31:30.23	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:31:30.27	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:31:31.54	SWS	43.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -25.0
10:31:37.98	SWS	-25.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:31:44.40	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -15.0
10:31:49.71	SWS	-15.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:31:54.97	SWS	44.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -15.0
10:32:00.38	SWS	-15.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:32:05.60	SWS	44.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -15.0
10:32:10.93	SWS	-15.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:32:16.29	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -15.0
10:32:21.54	SWS	-14.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:32:26.85	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -15.0
10:32:32.12	SWS	-14.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:32:37.32	SWS	43.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -15.0
10:32:42.58	SWS	-14.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:32:47.84	SWS	44.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -15.0
10:32:53.19	SWS	-15.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:32:58.40	SWS	44.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -15.0
10:33:03.66	SWS	-14.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:33:08.94	SWS	44.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -15.0
10:33:14.17	SWS	-14.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:33:19.43	SWS	44.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -15.0
10:33:24.70	SWS	-14.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:33:30.04	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -15.0
10:33:35.27	SWS	-14.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:33:40.45	SWS	43.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -15.0
10:33:45.68	SWS	-14.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:33:50.95	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -15.0
10:33:56.29	SWS	-15.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:34:01.55	SWS	44.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -15.0
10:34:06.81	SWS	-15.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:34:12.13	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -15.0
10:34:17.43	SWS	-15.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:34:22.71	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -15.0

10:34:27.96	SWS	-14.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:34:33.29	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -15.0
10:34:38.56	SWS	-14.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:34:43.87	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -15.0
10:34:49.11	SWS	-14.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:34:54.40	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -15.0
10:34:59.71	SWS	-15.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:35:04.99	SWS	44.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -15.0
10:35:10.34	SWS	-15.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:35:15.57	SWS	44.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -15.0
10:35:20.83	SWS	-15.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:35:26.18	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -15.0
10:35:31.54	SWS	-15.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:35:36.86	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -15.0
10:35:42.11	SWS	-15.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:35:47.50	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -15.0
10:35:52.80	SWS	-15.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:35:58.14	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -15.0
10:36:03.45	SWS	-15.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:36:08.71	SWS	44.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -15.0
10:36:14.00	SWS	-15.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:36:19.26	SWS	44.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -15.0
10:36:24.56	SWS	-15.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:36:29.84	SWS	44.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -15.0
10:36:35.08	SWS	-14.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:36:40.27	SWS	44.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -15.0
10:36:45.54	SWS	-14.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
10:36:50.82	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -15.0
10:36:55.29	SWS	-4.4	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:37:12.69	SWS	-4.4	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
10:37:22.06	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile descent (spiral)
10:37:24.95	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:37:24.96	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:37:24.97	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:37:25.81	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:37:26.10	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:37:26.32	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:37:27.58	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:37:27.59	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:37:27.62	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:37:28.47	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:37:28.65	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:37:28.95	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:37:40.15	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 6
10:38:52.23	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:38:52.25	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:38:52.33	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:38:53.10	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:38:53.37	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:38:53.56	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:42:14.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:42:21.24	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:42:21.31	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:42:21.32	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:42:22.17	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:42:22.42	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:42:22.63	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:42:23.95	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:42:23.95	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:42:23.97	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:42:24.83	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:42:25.02	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:42:25.31	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:42:26.88	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:42:26.95	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:42:26.97	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:42:27.36	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:42:27.56	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:42:27.73	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.

10:42:28.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:42:28.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:42:30.71	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:42:30.72	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:42:43.95	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:42:44.02	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:42:44.04	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:42:44.82	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:42:45.09	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:42:45.32	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:46:12.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:46:22.72	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:46:23.60	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:46:26.20	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:46:26.26	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:46:26.29	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:46:27.10	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:46:27.28	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:46:27.52	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:46:36.11	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:46:36.14	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:46:36.22	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:46:37.01	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:46:37.19	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:46:37.42	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:49:58.43	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:49:58.49	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:49:58.52	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:49:59.39	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:49:59.59	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:49:59.75	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:50:01.27	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:50:01.28	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:50:01.34	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:50:02.17	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:50:02.40	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:50:02.65	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:53:28.32	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:53:28.32	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:53:28.33	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:53:29.25	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:53:29.50	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:53:29.68	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:53:34.09	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:53:34.17	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:53:34.21	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:53:34.96	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:53:35.19	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:53:35.40	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:54:15.11	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:54:15.17	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:54:15.22	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:54:16.07	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:54:16.26	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:54:16.52	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:54:16.69	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:54:16.74	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:54:16.85	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:54:17.62	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:54:17.86	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:54:18.11	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:55:08.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:55:18.83	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:55:18.96	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:55:18.98	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:55:19.70	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:55:20.02	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:55:20.23	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:55:20.97	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.

10:55:21.09	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:55:21.11	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:55:21.84	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:55:22.11	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:55:22.34	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:55:22.79	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:55:22.82	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:55:22.83	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:55:23.82	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:55:24.03	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:55:24.33	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:55:25.89	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:55:25.96	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:55:25.98	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:55:26.77	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:55:27.03	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:55:27.33	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:57:13.19	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of profile descent
10:57:19.07	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:57:19.18	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:57:19.18	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:57:20.01	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:57:20.24	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:57:20.46	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:57:22.11	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:57:22.15	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:57:22.17	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
10:57:23.05	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:57:23.28	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:57:23.53	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
10:59:10.42	---	-	-	-	-	*** orbit 3 to the right
11:00:17.77	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of orbit
11:00:45.98	---	-	-	-	-	*** orbit 4 to the right 40 deg
11:02:36.62	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of orbit
11:02:39.71	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:02:39.75	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:02:39.81	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:02:40.69	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:02:41.00	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:02:41.22	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:02:51.59	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.000
11:02:55.34	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.000
11:03:03.44	---	-	-	-	-	*** orbit 5
11:03:11.91	---	-	-	-	-	*** 40 deg to the right again
11:04:45.92	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of orbit
11:04:48.31	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:04:48.36	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:04:48.41	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:04:49.20	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:04:49.44	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:04:49.64	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:04:50.19	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:04:50.21	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:04:50.26	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:04:51.08	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:04:51.34	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:04:51.53	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:04:52.32	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:04:52.34	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:04:52.40	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:04:53.23	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:04:53.41	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:04:53.66	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:05:11.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:05:16.88	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:05:16.97	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:05:16.98	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:05:17.73	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:05:18.00	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.

11:05:18.21	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:05:19.51	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:05:19.52	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:05:19.57	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:05:20.48	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:05:20.66	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:05:20.89	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:05:24.75	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:05:24.80	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:05:24.85	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:05:25.65	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:05:25.87	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:05:26.13	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:05:45.74	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:05:45.80	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:05:45.81	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:05:46.65	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:05:46.88	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:05:47.13	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:07:40.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:07:45.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:07:55.72	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:07:55.79	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:07:55.81	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:07:56.67	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:07:56.81	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:07:57.07	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:07:59.54	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:07:59.58	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:07:59.61	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:08:00.25	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:08:00.41	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:08:00.66	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:08:01.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:08:02.92	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:08:02.99	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:08:03.05	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:08:03.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:08:04.01	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:08:04.25	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:08:05.23	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:08:47.45	---	-	-	-	-	*** run from JFJ to A
11:08:51.20	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -4.000
11:08:57.28	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.000
11:09:01.31	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:09:09.49	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:09:17.18	SWS	-44.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:09:24.89	SWS	44.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:09:30.77	---	-	-	-	-	*** stray reflections between -25 and -40ish
11:09:33.12	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:09:41.30	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:09:49.46	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:09:57.67	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:10:05.83	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:10:14.01	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:10:22.18	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:10:30.42	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:10:38.11	SWS	-43.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:10:46.23	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:10:54.36	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:11:02.51	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:11:10.75	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:11:12.33	SWS	-30.2	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:11:18.42	SWS	-30.2	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
11:11:22.98	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:11:22.99	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:11:23.02	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:11:23.47	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:11:23.67	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.

11:11:23.83	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:11:24.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:11:24.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:11:27.11	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:11:27.11	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:11:27.22	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:11:28.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:11:28.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:11:28.46	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:11:30.43	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:11:30.44	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:12:02.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:15:02.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 13 from A to BADEP at FL 150
11:15:03.32	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.000
11:15:07.39	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:15:12.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:15:15.58	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:15:17.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:15:23.31	SWS	-44.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:15:31.50	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:15:39.66	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:15:46.36	---	-	-	-	-	*** stray reflections between 12 and 26 deg
11:15:47.37	SWS	43.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:15:55.53	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:16:03.78	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:16:11.47	SWS	-44.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:16:19.69	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:16:27.44	SWS	-44.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:16:35.59	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:16:43.82	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:16:52.06	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:17:00.32	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:17:03.35	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:17:03.39	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:17:03.39	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:17:04.28	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:17:04.48	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:17:04.73	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:17:05.08	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:17:05.89	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:17:05.93	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:17:06.02	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:17:06.58	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:17:06.77	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:17:07.01	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:17:07.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:17:08.41	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:17:08.86	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:17:16.61	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:17:24.36	SWS	44.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:17:32.55	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:17:40.27	SWS	44.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:17:48.49	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:17:56.68	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:18:04.42	SWS	-44.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:18:12.60	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:18:20.83	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:18:28.88	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:18:37.03	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:18:44.72	SWS	44.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:18:52.90	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:19:01.12	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:19:09.32	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:19:17.53	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:19:25.73	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:19:33.48	SWS	44.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:19:41.72	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:19:49.95	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:19:57.64	SWS	-43.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0

11:20:05.86	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:20:13.58	SWS	-44.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:20:21.80	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:20:30.03	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:20:37.74	SWS	44.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:20:45.95	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:20:54.14	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:21:01.90	SWS	-44.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:21:09.62	SWS	44.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:21:17.85	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:21:26.05	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:21:34.36	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:21:42.59	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:21:50.81	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:21:58.94	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:22:07.18	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:22:14.91	SWS	44.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:22:22.79	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:22:28.08	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:22:28.15	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:22:28.16	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:22:28.58	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:22:28.78	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:22:28.95	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:22:29.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:22:29.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:22:30.51	SWS	44.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:22:31.73	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:22:31.75	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:22:38.69	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:22:46.93	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:22:55.12	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:23:02.87	SWS	44.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:23:11.05	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:23:18.77	SWS	44.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:23:26.96	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:23:35.16	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:23:43.38	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:23:51.61	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:23:59.80	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:24:08.06	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:24:16.25	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:24:24.42	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:24:32.66	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:24:40.35	SWS	44.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:24:48.52	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:24:56.24	SWS	44.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:25:04.44	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:25:12.67	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:25:19.21	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:25:19.23	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:25:19.29	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:25:20.12	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:25:20.35	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:25:20.45	SWS	-44.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:25:20.55	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:25:28.64	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:25:36.67	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:25:44.56	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:25:52.77	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:26:00.53	SWS	44.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:26:08.28	SWS	-44.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:26:16.52	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:26:24.77	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:26:32.55	SWS	44.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:26:40.25	SWS	-44.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:26:47.98	SWS	44.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:26:55.71	SWS	-44.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:27:03.92	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0

11:27:12.12	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:27:19.83	SWS	44.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:27:28.10	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:27:33.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:27:35.83	SWS	44.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:27:37.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:27:42.10	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:27:42.10	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:27:42.18	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:27:42.78	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:27:43.05	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:27:43.26	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:27:43.67	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:27:43.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:27:44.43	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:27:44.48	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:27:44.56	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:27:45.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:27:45.57	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:27:45.76	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:27:46.76	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:27:49.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:27:51.44	SWS	44.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
11:27:52.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:27:53.66	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:27:53.70	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:27:53.73	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:27:54.57	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:27:54.75	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:27:54.96	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:27:55.42	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:27:55.49	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:27:55.50	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:27:56.34	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:27:56.64	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:27:56.83	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:27:57.27	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:27:57.32	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:27:57.37	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:27:58.17	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:27:58.42	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:27:58.65	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:27:59.24	SWS	-45.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
11:28:03.76	SWS	4.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:28:10.58	SWS	4.9	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
11:28:13.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:28:13.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:28:13.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:28:15.22	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:28:18.46	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:28:18.46	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:28:18.48	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:28:19.16	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:28:19.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:28:19.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:28:20.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:28:20.37	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:28:20.38	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:28:20.38	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:28:21.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:28:21.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:28:21.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:28:21.97	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:28:21.97	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:28:22.02	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:29:58.84	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:29:58.93	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:29:58.97	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:29:59.72	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.

11:29:59.96	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:30:00.25	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:30:01.30	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:30:01.32	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:30:01.38	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:30:02.17	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:30:02.43	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:30:02.62	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:36:30.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:36:46.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:42:01.48	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:42:01.53	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:42:01.53	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:42:02.40	LSH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:42:02.58	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:42:02.77	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:42:04.11	SWS	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:42:04.14	USH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:42:04.18	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:42:04.80	LSH	-	-	40	40	Dark measurement started.
11:42:04.96	SWS	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.
11:42:05.26	USH	-	-	40	40	Manual scene recording started.